

Open-MOLLI for All: Advancing Open-Source, Vendor-Agnostic T1-mapping One System at a Time, Now on GE!

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INTRODUCTION: Standardization of MR quantitative measures is crucial for reproducible results that can be reliably used in the clinic to distinguish healthy from pathological tissues [1-3]. However, the implementation of techniques such as T1 mapping is known to vary between vendors, affecting reproducibility and hindering the method's applicability for clinical diagnostic and follow-up. Precise pulse sequence matching across centers and vendors has been shown to improve reproducibility [4] (e.g. VENUS [1] and Pulseseq [5]).

The open-source myocardial T1 mapping (Open-MOLLI) sequence [6,7] was previously developed to enable reproducible cardiac T1-mapping. Open-MOLLI has since been tested in different Siemens systems (1.5 T and 3.0T) and compared to the vendor MOLLI implementations. It was shown to provide comparable myocardial T1 values with equivalent same-scan repeatability [8]. In this work, we extend the Open-MOLLI method and adapt the sequence to comply with specific GE requirements, demonstrating the feasibility to run it also on GE systems.

METHODS: MOLLI consists of an inversion-recovery (IR) sequence for quantitative T1 parameter estimation (T1 mapping). Open-MOLLI uses trigger scheme 5(3)3. It is publicly available at <https://github.com/asgaspar/OpenMOLLI>. Open-MOLLI was adapted for the GE system using TOPPE [9] by labelling the sequence into 4 blocks: the inversion pulse, the readout, the delay between readouts and the delay after inversion. The GE implementation of Open-MOLLI was tested on 2 healthy subjects (2M) in a 3T Signa PET-MR scanner using a 32 channel Head Coil.

The acquisition was performed in one axial brain slice, and the mean T1 was estimated in white (WM) and grey matter (GM) manually delineated regions of interest. Open-MOLLI with an under-sampling factor of 2 had the following parameters: field-of-view of 354 × 327 mm², matrix size 256×144, slice thickness of 8 mm, TR/TE=3.24/3.12 ms, flip angle of 35°, readout bandwidth 808 Hz/pixel, with shortest inversion time (TI) of 183 ms. The sequence timing was built according to a (simulated) heart rate of 60 bpm. Data reconstruction was performed offline using GRAPPA, and T1 estimation with 3-parameter analytic model using the magnitude signals was done in Matlab [3].

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: Open-MOLLI was successfully implemented on GE. Figure 1a shows the T1-weighted images obtained for 2 subjects. Figure 2b shows the T1 maps estimated for each subject. The mean T1 values for each region of interest are presented in Table 1, along with their standard deviations and the respective T1 literature values for GM and WM at 3.0T. The mean T1 over the two subjects was 772±22 ms for WM, and 1244±72 ms for GM, which is in agreement with the literature (T1_{WM}=860 ms and T1_{GM}=1200 ms)[10-13]. The work is a proof-of-concept of the applicability of Open-MOLLI to a vendor (GE) different from that in which it was originally implemented (Siemens). We were able to estimate T1 values for the brain (GM and WM) that are consistent with those reported in the literature at 3.0T. The adaptation of the Open-MOLLI T1-mapping sequence to the GE system required changes in the sequence that remain compatible with previously used Siemens systems. The current GE Open-MOLLI implementation still lacks the cardiac-triggering capabilities required for myocardial T1-mapping, which are the focus of ongoing work.

CONCLUSION: This work demonstrates the applicability of Open-MOLLI in GE systems, paving the way for future inter-scanner reproducibility studies.

Figure 1 – T1 mapping in vivo with Open-MOLLI in GE: **a.** Mean T1 (in ms) per region; **b.** T1-weighted images for two healthy subjects with TI=183 ms, and respective, **c.** T1 maps (in ms). Region of interest for white matter (white) and grey matter (black) are represented, with respective mean T1 and standard deviation.

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